

FAME Business Framework Documentation

Contributing Organisations

Version 1.0

May 2025

Publisher

FAME Consortium,
2025

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FAME Consortium,
2025

Editor

Konstantina Tripodi, JRC Capital Management

Authors & Contributors

Konstantina Tripodi, JRC Capital Management

Marcus Nasarek, etonec

Jana Peliova, Ekonomická univerzita v
Bratislave

Zuzana Brokešová, Ekonomická univerzita v
Bratislave

Nelia Zinatullina, eco

Giacomo Delinavelli, Arthur's Legal

Geert Machtenlickx, Fujitsu

Samrat Gupta, Universitetet i Agder - Indian
Institute of Management Ahmedabad

Ernesto Troiano, GFT

Antonio Sottosanti, GFT

Valentina Buttol, GFT

Executive Summary

*This document outlines the **Business Framework** for the FAME Marketplace, a platform designed to facilitate secure and efficient data exchanges between various stakeholders, including businesses, consumers, and service providers. The primary objective is to define a sustainable and scalable business model that provides value to customers while ensuring long-term growth and profitability. The marketplace aims to address key market needs by offering high-quality data, AI-driven insights, and transparent transactions.*

The objective of a business model in FAME is to establish a structured and secure environment for the exchange, monetization, and utilization of data. In general, data marketplaces act as intermediaries connecting data providers with data consumers, facilitating transactions while ensuring data quality, privacy, and compliance with regulations. The primary goal is to create value from data assets by enabling businesses, researchers, and developers to access relevant datasets that can drive insights, innovation, and decision-making. A well-designed business model for a data marketplace identifies the key participants—data suppliers, consumers, and platform operators—and defines the mechanisms for data pricing, access, and usage rights. It ensures a seamless transaction process while maintaining trust through robust security measures and transparent governance.

The approach involves developing a comprehensive framework that includes a clear value proposition, customer segmentation, resource identification, revenue models, and key partnerships. The business model focuses on three core revenue streams: transaction fees, subscription-based services, and tokenization, providing flexibility and adaptability in the ever-evolving data market. Sustainability is emphasized through long-term viability strategies, including continuous innovation and expansion to new markets. Challenges such as regulatory concerns, security risks, and market competition are thoroughly analyzed, with mitigation strategies outlined to ensure a robust and secure platform.

The document concludes with case studies showcasing successful business models in the data marketplace and provides insights from both successes and failures, offering valuable lessons for future development. Key questions for collaboration and next steps are identified to guide the continued evolution of the business model. Additionally, the glossary provides definitions for key terms to ensure clarity and consistency throughout the document.

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1 Business Model Overview

1.1 Introduction

Data became one of the most crucial industry resources in our economy. More and more data-driven business models emerge and replace manufacturing industry or impact these traditional businesses significantly. Simultaneously, it became clear that data needs to be authentic, its integrity and confidentiality requires protection, and reliable processing needs to be carried out under the umbrella of certain compliance frameworks. To leverage the scalability and efficiency of digital processing it has to be facilitated by respective technologies which allow trusted and compliant interactions, and not to forget: the monetization of data.

The FAME Marketplace facilitates the exchange of valuable data and insights. It is driven by key factors such as increasing demand for data-driven decisions, technological advancements, and regulatory changes. The marketplace enables businesses to buy, sell, and share data securely and transparently. Establishing a marketplace that takes care of the discoverability of demanded services, interoperability between the parties, that ensures the identity of the actors, and fosters regulatory compliance helps to make data-driven business models scalable.

To achieve these goals with traditional concepts scalability can quickly become a burden, as managing trust and compliance in a multi-stakeholder environment is costly and complex. Therefore, the FAME Marketplace uses multiple components which formed in the recent years, for example tokenization and decentralized identities, rather than web 1.0 technologies, which were never designed for an economy highly depending on reliability and legal certainty.

This said, the value for the platform users can be summarized as to enable them to scale their business at lower costs. That proposition holds for both sides of the two-sided business model of the platform: the platform lifts the efforts on customer acquisition and product provision for the data providers on the one side and low efforts on data acquisition as well as legal certainty for data consumers on the other side.

As the core of all business models is to generate revenue, there are two aspects to consider. One, the revenue of the platform and how it relates to the usage of the marketplace. The platform's revenue should grow with increasing usage and size of deals on the marketplace to establish a sustainable business for the platform. Second, the revenue the data providers make based on their product provision on the marketplace. The platform should provide functionalities to allow for high margins due to low costs and thus, attract more data providers to the marketplace.

The details of the business model schematically described above will be provided in this document to allow a better understanding of how the marketplace's customers can leverage the FAME Marketplace to accelerate their data driven business models.

1.2 Objective of the Business Model

The objective of the business model is to provide a sustainable and scalable blueprint for data driven businesses. It outlines the value offered to customers, defines target audiences, and identifies the ways the business will generate revenue. The model also focuses on long-term growth and adaptability to market changes.

The goal is to show how a marketplace for data exchange can generate more revenue for its customers when they have to deal with digital goods in environments that are highly regulated or rapidly changing, so long-term scaling is challenging.

The business model laid out in this document also should show how new technologies, such as blockchain, digital identity wallets, and asset tokenization, can be leveraged to achieve the goals.

Therefore, it's of outmost importance to understand the roles of the stakeholders in this system and to recognize the current change of the European economy's needs, specifically a high degree of regulation and decreasing availability of qualified workforce. The business model should show how joining forces on a pan-European scale in the form of a marketplace is possible and allows for growth, enabling a more neutral setup in the middle than the existing commercial intermediaries.

1.3 Roles in the Business Model

The following figure provides an overview of the roles in the FAME Marketplace ecosystem when the full potential of the marketplaces unfolds.

1. The data provider: the data provider creates, aggregates, or forwards data from authentic sources and offers them to data consumers.
2. The data consumer: the data consumer demands data for its business purposes, for further processing, or enabling other businesses or consumers with services based on the data.
3. The trust service provider: the trust service provider serves the marketplace participants with the required trust anchors, as there are key services, signature services, e.g. to ensure the respective level of assurance of identities and data authenticity.
4. The marketplace data connector: the marketplace connector enables marketplace participants to interact with the platform at minimal efforts, e.g. if they do not want to invest in building their own marketplace connectivity components or if services fall under a certain regulatory framework, they do not want to implement by themselves.
5. The data custodian: the data custodian safeguards digital assets on behalf of market participants. They ensure compliance with certain regulations and facilitate asset management procedures, like multiple-authorization procedures, delegation, data escrow, data deposits, etc.
6. The marketplace operator: the marketplace operator provides and maintains the technical platform and essentially operates the marketplace. Its responsibility is the onboarding of

- marketplace participants, the continuous further development of the platform, adopted schemes, and the governance of the marketplace ecosystem.
7. The regulator: there are multiple possible regulatory regimes which apply to the marketplace, whereas the marketplace participants are responsible for regulatory compliance within their own domain, the marketplace itself is a pan-European technology provider offering an infrastructure which must allow its users to comply to their respective law. This said, there are certain requirements to be considered depending on the connected service
 8. The payment provider: the payment service provider facilitates the monetization of data consumptions. That role can have different flavors from processing a one-off purchase to processing payments on demand, multi-currency transactions, multiple payment flows (data provider-initiated, data consumer-initiated, split payments, installments, payment at delivery, etc.). But it can also be a liquidity pool provider for units of account to facilitate micro payments, conditional payments or automated payments driven by smart contracts or other automatisms.

Some roles are essential from the beginning, as there are the data provider, the data consumer and the marketplace operator. Others will enter the ecosystem once demanded and the separation of duties take shape.

2 Core Business Model Concepts for Stakeholders

2.1 Value Proposition

As a two-sided business model, the platform needs to attract customers with value propositions for both the data providers and the data consumers.

The value proposition for the data providers can be summarized as reducing the customer acquisition costs and allowing for scaling the business at lower costs.

The value proposition for data consumers includes the availability of high-quality, curated data and AI-driven insights to help them make informed decisions. It also includes to get provide with a secure and transparent environment for data exchange, ensuring privacy and compliance with regulations. Data consumers can access unique datasets that would otherwise be difficult to obtain.

The next sections will provide more details to these assumptions.

2.1.1 Value Proposition Data Providers

The value proposition for data providers, including pilot partners, emphasizes tailored solutions that address their specific needs and challenges. Key benefits include:

- **Ease of Use:** A user-friendly platform that simplifies the complexities of data exchange. This reduces the integration costs and adoption of the functionalities provided by the platform.
- **Support for Providers in Pricing of Digital Assets (smart assets monetization):** FAME provides unique Price advisory tool (PAT). PAT offers price recommendations for assets and digital products based on user inputs. The price ranges suggested by PAT are computed based on the static characteristics of similar assets as well as dynamicity of demand of similar assets (to the focal data asset) on the platform.
- **Broader market reach:** data providers can gain greater visibility to a wider pool of potential buyers, opening new revenue opportunities and lowering acquisition costs
- **Data sovereignty and federated governance:** data providers are able to retain full ownership and control of their assets, while also trust and accountability are ensured
- **Single Entry/Access Point:** simplifies the complexity of managing, sharing, trading and analyzing data assets through a streamlined federated platform
- **Secure and interoperable:** FAME offers a secure, standard-based, and interoperable data and analytics marketplace, ensuring data sovereignty, privacy, security, and trustworthiness.
- **Cutting edge technologies for efficiency and security:** FAME leverages advanced technologies such as semantic interoperability to enable seamless data exchange across different platforms, blockchain-based trust mechanisms, and adaptive authentication, perfectly integrated to ensure efficient, secure, and responsible data sharing
- **Compliance with EU regulations by design:** FAME enables users to operate in a secure and compliant environment by incorporating tools and processes that comply with European laws, while also aligning with stringent financial regulations. Platform players are then able to scale their business without having to worry about legal hurdles
- **Customization Options:** Tools and services that cater to individual preferences and business requirements. Customers can choose from certain services to retrieve a tailor-made integration and adjust the functionality to their business needs.
- **Engagement and Support:** Robust mechanisms for feedback, loyalty, and continuous improvement.

The overarching aim for the provision to data providers is to enhance user experience and deliver measurable benefits, such as cost savings, time efficiency, and enhanced performance.

2.1.2 Value Proposition Data Consumers

The value proposition for data consumers addresses the challenge of seamlessly discovering, integrating, and leveraging high-quality data in a secure, compliant, and efficient manner to unlock business value and accelerate innovation. Key benefits include:

- **Customization Options:** As for data providers also for data consumers the tools and services that cater to individual preferences and business requirements. Customers can choose from certain services to retrieve a tailor-made integration and adjust the functionality to their business needs.
- **Wider range of data sources:** data consumers can gain greater visibility to a wider and potentially more qualitative pool of potential data assets, opening new sources to the often data-hungry applications that these consumers are building
- **Accelerated product development and Enhanced Productivity:** Improved workflows and data quality, leading to better decision-making and efficiency, and shorter time-to-market for new products and services.
- **Single Entry/Access Point:** simplifies the complexity of accessing, managing, and analyzing data assets through a streamlined federated platform
- **Access to high-value assets:** consumers can easily discover specialized datasets, advanced analytics and ready-to-use AI models
- **Secure and interoperable marketplace:** FAME offers a secure, standard-based, and interoperable data and analytics marketplace, ensuring data sovereignty, privacy, security, and trustworthiness
- **Cutting edge technologies for efficiency and security:** FAME leverages advanced technologies such as semantic interoperability to enable seamless data gathering across different platforms, blockchain-based trust mechanisms, and adaptive authentication, perfectly integrated to ensure efficient, secure, and responsible data sourcing
- **Compliance with EU regulations by design:** FAME enables users to operate in a secure and compliant environment by incorporating tools and processes that comply with European laws, while also aligning with stringent financial regulations. Platform players are then able to scale their business without having to worry about legal hurdles

The primary goal for data consumers is to provide a frictionless, trustworthy channel for sourcing high-quality data assets, ultimately enhancing user experience and fueling data-driven growth.

2.1.3 Value Proposition for other Stakeholders

As shown in the section ‘Roles in the Business Model’ there can be more stakeholders in the marketplace ecosystem once it evolves over time. As an outlook to a possible extension of the marketplace to additional customer segments of the marketplace, the value proposition for these parties can be briefly summarized as the following:

The marketplace data connector: the marketplace provides marketplace connectors with new market opportunities. As companies usually have preferred providers, they will ask them to act as marketplace connector. Due to the spirit of standardized interfaces and data formats, these vendors can expand to more potential clients in their role as marketplace connector.

The data custodian: the trade of digital assets will quickly ask for temporary or permanent custody of these assets. The marketplace offers an easy way to expand their business.

The payment provider: The need for different types of payment in the marketplace provides room for the services of multiple payment providers including the respective principal bank of an individual customer. The easy integration of payment services into the platform attracts payment service providers to offer their services to the marketplace users.

Overall, for other stakeholders of the marketplace, the value proposition revolves around the strategic and financial benefits the business model provides to them. This includes offering a return on investment (ROI) through profitability, growth potential, and market expansion. Partners and suppliers benefit from mutually advantageous collaborations, shared resources, and new opportunities for distribution or co-branding. Risk management, long-term sustainability, and alignment with stakeholder goals, such as profitability and market positioning, are critical. Additionally, the model supports transparency, ethical practices, and stakeholder engagement, ensuring long-term value and competitive advantage for all parties involved. The overall approach aims to foster strong, sustainable relationships and shared success.

2.2 Customer Segments

The FAME Marketplace caters to a diverse range of customers, encompassing four primary segments. Data providers, which include individuals and organizations, seek to monetize their data assets. Data consumers, ranging from small businesses to large enterprises, rely on marketplace data for research, marketing, and strategic decision-making. Third-party developers use the data to create innovative products and services. Finally, regulators ensure that all transactions conducted within the marketplace comply with legal and ethical standards, reinforcing trust and accountability in the ecosystem.

2.3 Key Resources

The success of the FAME Marketplace relies on several critical resources. Advanced technology infrastructure, including cloud services and AI-powered tools, ensures seamless data processing and secure transactions. A robust data governance framework safeguards privacy and compliance with regulatory standards, fostering trust and credibility. Additionally, skilled human resources across technology, business development, and legal compliance play a crucial role in driving the marketplace's operations and innovation. These resources collectively enable the marketplace to deliver on its promises and meet the diverse needs of its users and stakeholders.

2.4 Key Partnerships

2.4.1.1 Technology Providers

- **Cloud Services:** Secure, scalable infrastructure is crucial for data exchange. Cloud providers ensure reliable storage, fast access, and data redundancy.
- **AI & Analytics:** AI-driven insights enhance data discoverability, automate data categorization, and provide value-added analytics.
- **Security & Encryption:** Ensuring data protection through encryption, access control, and threat detection mechanisms is vital for marketplace trust.
- **Identity & Authentication Services:** Secure identity verification and Single Sign-On (SSO) solutions help validate actors in the marketplace.

2.4.1.2 Data Providers

- **Enterprise Data Suppliers:** Large organizations with proprietary datasets (financial, healthcare, retail, etc.) contribute high-value data.
- **Government & Public Data Sources:** Open data initiatives and regulatory bodies may provide demographic, economic, or environmental data.
- **IoT & Sensor Data Aggregators:** Companies collecting real-time sensor data (smart cities, industrial IoT) offer insights for various industries.

- **Alternative Data Providers:** Emerging sources such as satellite imagery, geospatial data, or consumer behavior analytics provide unique market advantages.
- **Research Institutions:** Universities, laboratories, and academic consortia generate specialized datasets through scientific studies, clinical trials, and experimental research, offering rigorously validated information.

2.4.1.3 Regulatory Bodies

- **Data Privacy Compliance:** Ensuring adherence to GDPR, CCPA, and other data privacy laws through standardized contracts and automated compliance checks.
- **Security & Data Sovereignty:** Partnering with regulators to ensure secure cross-border data exchanges and compliance with national laws.
- **Ethical AI & Fair Use:** Collaborations to promote ethical AI models and prevent data misuse within the marketplace.

2.4.1.4 Other Marketplaces

- **Interoperability Standards:** Partnerships with similar marketplaces to ensure seamless data exchange and compatibility across platforms.
- **Extended Data Access:** Expanding the marketplace's reach by integrating with third-party data sources or industry-specific marketplaces.
- **Blockchain & Smart Contracts:** Enabling trusted, automated transactions between marketplaces to ensure transparency and auditability.

By fostering strategic collaborations, **FAME Marketplace** creates a dynamic and secure ecosystem that enhances data exchange and utilization. AI-powered search and categorization improve **discoverability**, ensuring businesses can easily access relevant datasets. **Interoperability** is achieved through standardized APIs and data formats, enabling seamless integration between different platforms and industries. Strong **security and trust** measures, including identity verification, encryption, and compliance frameworks, safeguard transactions and protect sensitive data. Furthermore, a **scalable** technological foundation supports widespread adoption, allowing the marketplace to expand globally while maintaining efficiency and reliability. These partnerships collectively drive innovation, transparency, and growth in data-driven business models.

3 Revenue Models for FAME

The economic rationale for each role to participate in the marketplace ecosystem can be summarized as the following:

1. The data provider: data providers can have multiple economic incentives to connect to the FAME Marketplace.
 - a. Trading data at a higher margin due to lower cost (provision costs, customer acquisition cost, technical interoperability cost) and more revenue (bigger market reach, more visibility)
 - b. Comply with regulation at lower costs (adopt industry best practices, rely on the platform's implementation approach to regulatory requirements)
 - c. Faster Go-to-market due to the availability of a provision infrastructure that is ready to use.
 - d. Less complexity due to offloading common services for many value chain elements as there are but not limited to: customer onboarding, customer interaction, mutual authentication, regulatory compliance, monetization and billing, etc.
2. The data consumer: data consumers can have multiple economic incentives to use the platform as a data source:
 - a. Sourcing data at lower cost due to the outsourcing of data mining and data warehousing
 - b. Lower integration costs due to the use of standards cross multiple data providers, and the use of platform components for onboarding, data exchange, mutual authentication, regulatory compliance
 - c. Comply with regulation at lower costs (adopt industry best practices, rely on the platform's implementation approach to regulatory requirements)
 - d. Faster Go-to-market due to the visibility of existing providers and availability of a data sourcing infrastructure that is ready to use.
3. The marketplace operator/provider: the marketplace operators' economic rationale is to get fees for the service provision which scales fast with the network effect of connecting customers (data provider and data consumers. The efficiency of providing standard components for the data exchange value chain between the platform participants acts as a multiplier for each component the customers can rely on and outsource to the platform.

In addition to the basic ecosystem with the 3 core roles described above, other roles will establish as soon as the platform gets traction and scales. For example, will a data connector provide simplified integration services and enable new participants to connect with little effort if there is sufficient demand to justify such a service. This is also the case for data custodians who provide secure and compliant storage for digital assets. They will provide services when regulated digital assets are traded and escrow or deposit services are demanded. The payment service provider will enter the scene once the collection and remittance of payments between multiple parties requires more sophisticated processing than bilateral invoicing.

In the following we focus on the 3 core roles of the FAME Marketplace ecosystem. The financial model for the FAME Marketplace based on these 3 core roles is shown in the figure below.

Fees to be paid by the data provider to the marketplace operator:

1. Onboarding fees: onboarding fees may be paid to compensate for the onboarding and integration costs.
2. Component Service fees: the FAME Marketplace offers multiple components, for example identification services (e.g. EUDI based), customer billing, compliance services, storage, etc. either as optional services or as separate billing items. These services are paid as a periodic billing item.
3. Usage fees: based on the platform usage there are one or more usage fees to be paid by the data provider to the marketplace.

Fees to be paid by the data consumer to the marketplace operator:

1. Onboarding fees: onboarding fees may be paid to compensate for the onboarding and integration costs.
2. Component Service fees: the FAME Marketplace offers multiple components, for example identification services (e.g. EUDI based), customer billing, compliance services, storage, etc. either as optional services or as separate billing items. These services are paid as a periodic billing item.
3. Usage fees: based on the platform usage there are one or more usage fees to be paid by the data consumer to the marketplace.

Fees to be paid by the data consumer to the data provider:

1. Fee per record: a simple transaction-based fee model where defined data records are paid per item. As a precondition it needs to be defined what a data record specifically is and how the items are counted. Tiers, kickbacks, and discounts may apply.
2. Periodical subscription fees: To simplify billing in high volume or high frequent data provision of similar items, a subscription model may apply. Based on the data characteristics and value a monthly or annual fee can be agreed on to compensate the data consumption.
3. Value based fee: in cases where the data provision is related to the value of the data, e.g. there is a risk, liability, production effort, etc., a fee based on certain metrics may apply. That may be a share of the monetary value, a ratio to the energy of creation, or a multiplier driven by the demand.

3.1 Transaction Fees

Transaction fees are related to some countable units which need to be defined very specifically. If the data record to be exchanged on the marketplace has a clearly defined format, size, and/or content it can be mapped to a metrics which is comparable and countable.

To achieve this the following steps are to be applied:

1. Define the schemes for tradable data records in a way the records have similar size or value being treated as on unit
2. Implement a counting mechanism considering single transactions and batches of transactions.
3. Estimate the number of transactions (NT) that will be processed in a given period. The estimation can be based on the servable obtainable market size to be converted in a given timeframe. The period is usually twice the time to break even for new ventures in a new market.
4. Take into account comparable pricings (CP) in the competitive environment as a benchmark.
5. Divide the operational costs (OPEX) to provide the marketplace processing costs by the number of transactions (NT) in the given period and align with the competitive benchmark.

Transaction fee (TF) = OPEX/NT + Margin for full cost coverage by transaction fees.

Correction Factor (CF) = CP/TF

If the correction factor is less than 1, there is the need to reduce OPEX or to defend the unique selling point.

To cover a static share of the OPEX a base fee can cover a baseline cost, with the majority of variable costs being covered in the transaction fee.

The applicability of transaction fees depends on the ratio of variable costs to fixed cost in the OPEX. If there are clearly defined units of transactions, and transaction objects can be easily scoped as well if there is a high volatility in the volume over a given period, a transaction-based fee is more attractive to customers. If the vast majority of costs are pretty static, a subscription model may appear fairer.

3.2 Subscriptions

The platform offers subscription-based access, allowing customers to pay a recurring fee for access to the platform, to premium data, insights, or features. This provides a steady, predictable income.

Subscription fees are an important component of a financial plan to support investment strategies, reliable planning of resources, and managing the risk of the business. This is even more relevant if the service usage or processed volume is hard to predict, which is often the case in the establishment phase of a venture.

One downside of subscription fees is the entry barrier they are building up for customers not yet familiar with the service. The objective of a good pricing model is to optimize the balance between the subscription fee margin and the number of prospect churn.

The approach of identifying a profitable subscription model is the following:

1. Fixed Costs (FC): Identify the share of fixed costs (salary, infrastructure, licenses, etc.) related to the service
2. Variable Costs (VC): Identify the share of the average variable costs which are driven by the usage (transactions, computation, third party services, etc.)
3. Number of Customers (NC): Estimate the number of customers who can be acquired in the given period of the financial plan which is twice the time to break even.

4. Time to break even (TBE): Whereas the time to break even is given by the investment plan, e.g. counted in months.
5. Divide the fixed costs for the period by the number of customers in that period

Subscription Fee low boundary (SFLB) = $FC/(NC*2TBE)$, e.g. in fee / month

A rough estimate for the lower boundary of a subscription should cover fixed costs plus a certain margin, with a flexible pricing mechanism to account for fluctuating variable costs based on usage or demand.

The flexible pricing mechanism to incorporate the costs related to the actual usage can be either

a) put on top of the subscription fee a unit fee (UF) based on some metrics like number of transactions, consumed volume units, computation units, or service delivery units, e.g. units per month (SU), whereas $UF*SU$ should at least cover VC plus a certain buffer correlating with the standard deviation of the variable costs variation.

Subscription Fee (SF) = $SFLB + UF*SU$. in fee / month

Or b) being estimated (UE) and incorporated into the subscription fee with some margin (M).

Subscription Fee (SF) = $SFLB + UE + M$. in fee / month

The model preferred by customers relies on multiple factors:

- Their understanding of how many service units they generate (number of transactions in the contract timeline) and how big the business provided on the marketplace will be.
- the anticipated fairness of a subscription model related to competing services or alternative ways of business provision exist.
- The terms and conditions to adopt changes of their business, or if the predicted business does not match the actual traction

There are two phases of the subscription fee model. In an initial phase a subscription fee that is low enough to attract initial customers and being subsidized as a customer acquisition cost. This phase can be defined by a certain goal for the number of initial customers. This number should be a significant step on the way to break even.

When reliable traction is reached another phase based on the actual cost and of usage measures a subscription fee model calculated from KPIs based on that data. This model is the operational model for continuous growth.

3.3 Tokenization

The use of distributed ledgers and its smart contract capabilities allow for more flexible fee models. Not only can a blockchain application provide the delivery of digital assets or data access credentials, it can also combine the payment with the underlying delivery. This combination of the payment with the underlying business supports fully automated reconciliation of smallest fractions of a payment unit to nearly neglectable costs, which comes very handy in cases the usage units is highly volatile or the execution of payment transfers builds up on small contributors from a highly distributed system.

The programmable fee model is extremely flexible and beyond the simple example above with relatively little effort it can support, for example:

1. escrow payments, where certain conditions automatically trigger a payment. The marketplace can improve the trust model, by allowing data consumers to stake the funds and releasing them to the data provider if certain criteria of delivery are fulfilled, whereas a certain commission fee is automatically transferred to the marketplace.

2. pre-authorized rule-based payment reconciliation. For example can data consumers parameterize smart contract to transfer funds from their token deposits if a certain party providing a certain proof, whereas the platform as the proof issuer will atomically receive a facilitator fee.
3. Many but small fees, e.g. a sensor-initiated event from thousands of sensors each demanding only a fraction of a cent and contributing on an irregular basis can be continuously accumulated as blockchain based token and immediately and reliably settled if certain conditions apply, e.g. periodically or threshold-driven.

The examples above are only a very small peek into the options of possible fee models that can be realized with the tokenization of values. To generalize the approach the implementation model is following:

- A token represents a certain value
- Tokens are held in accounts on blockchain infrastructure and can also be controlled through the use of smart contracts
- There can be fee models linked to the token, specific for the respective use case, whereas the FAME Marketplace is the beneficiary of the fees
- Data providers and data consumers can be account owners of a token account and can control the transfer of tokens by their services on the platform.
- Tokens can be redeemed against EUR amounts which will be withdrawn to a bank account

With this model the marketplace can earn revenue from automated delivery systems at very little operational costs. The use of distributed ledgers and its smart contract capabilities allow for more flexible fee models.

4 Sustainability

4.1 Long-Term Viability

The long-term viability of the business model in the context of the marketplace's B2B services is based on strong and long-lasting customer relationships. The customer acquisition costs which are proportionally higher in innovative businesses compared to traditional products where there is less need to explain the product and to educate prospects, need to be compensated with continuous revenue from existing customers. A subscription model based on a long-term contract would be the natural expression of this solid customer relationship. The focus should therefore be on winning new customers subscribing to the service, extending the business with the existing customer base, and increasing usage of the platform.

To maintain a long-lasting customer relationship the marketplace ensures sustainability by focusing on continuous innovation, high-quality data, customer trust, and adapting to evolving market demands. Regulatory compliance and strong data protection mechanisms are central to maintaining long-term viability. Also, long-term viability in data marketplaces depends on the sustained ability to provide high-quality, secure, and accessible data while adapting to evolving technological, regulatory, and market conditions. Key factors include maintaining data quality and integrity, fostering trust through transparency, and ensuring compliance with privacy regulations. Robust technological infrastructure is crucial, requiring scalable cloud systems, privacy-enhancing technologies, and secure APIs. The marketplace must also prioritize data interoperability, standardization, and user-friendly interfaces to attract a broad range of participants.

The result of strong customer relationships is a predictable revenue stream and possible growth of the turnover by attracting new customers based on the replication effect (new customers do what others already do); it also helps to maintain a financial plan to reduce capital procurement costs for scaling.

To extend the business with existing customers, may it be by volume and additional services, the marketplace should support and simplify the process of data providers to approach and serve data consumers. It should be as easy as possible for customers to add new services to their profile or to adjust the capacity and commercial rates.

To achieve a profitable impact on the business model, additional services need to be effortlessly discoverable in the context of using the platform, so customers can easily adapt and integrate with these additional services. If more usage and platform capacities are acquired by the customers, the commercial model should be seamlessly adjusted to the new demand (pay-by-demand, see scaling aspects below) and allow the customer to focus on its core business.

To avoid hesitation because of unpredictable costs when the customer adds new services or higher volumes to its current use of the marketplace, there should be a cost estimation service helping the customer with more transparency and cost prediction.

In other words, as the FAME Marketplace scales by the number of customers and the use of its services, it will need to adapt to evolving regulatory environments and increasing data complexity. Compliance frameworks thus have to be flexible and capable of scaling to accommodate global regulations like GDPR, and other EU-specific privacy laws. Regular updates and proactive adjustments to data protection measures will be essential to ensure continued compliance. FAME's viability will also depend heavily on its ability to maintain trust with users. Data providers, end users, and other stakeholders will expect the marketplace to demonstrate a strong commitment to security and regulatory compliance. A failure to protect user data or adhere to regulations could damage the marketplace's reputation, leading to decreased user adoption and potential legal repercussions.

4.2 Scaling the Business Model

Scaling the FAME Marketplace business model is essential to achieve sustainable growth and maximize its market impact. This phase focuses on expanding the platform's reach, optimizing its operations, and enhancing its adaptability to meet evolving market demands and user needs. By strategically refining key elements of the business model, the marketplace will unlock new opportunities for growth while maintaining operational efficiency and delivering value to all stakeholders.

The first step in scaling involves broadening the marketplace's customer base by targeting additional industries and geographies. While initial efforts focused on pilot partners and specific sectors, the platform must now expand its reach to a wider array of data providers, consumers, third-party developers, and regulators. A comprehensive marketing and outreach strategy will play a crucial role in achieving this expansion, supported by partnerships and collaborations that increase the marketplace's visibility and credibility in new domains.

Another critical aspect of scaling is optimizing the operational governance module (GOV) to handle increased demand and complexity. This involves enhancing the capabilities of core components such as Federation Management, User Management, User Support, and Trading Support. For instance, the integration of additional service endpoints and the implementation of advanced automation will ensure seamless user experiences, efficient onboarding, and robust support systems. Additionally, continuous updates to the platform's underlying technology infrastructure, including cloud services and AI tools, will maintain scalability and performance as the marketplace grows.

Scaling is only profitable if standards can be used, and customer-specific services are not driving the customer acquisition in small niches as pre-investments of the marketplace. Nevertheless, there will be individual needs per customer and the platform should support these customer-side adjustments by either providing a flexible (e.g. open API-based, modularized, or plug-in-based) way of customization or a developer zone / marketplace for platform extensions/customizations to use the force of a community.

The more the impact of the scaling is carried by technology, automation, and standards, the less is the correlation with expensive human resources and the higher the margin or competitive advantage with regards to pricing strategy.

To ensure financial sustainability, the business model will refine and expand its monetization strategies. This includes diversifying revenue streams by introducing new pricing tiers for subscription-based models, developing advanced pay-as-you-go (PAYG) and pay-as-you-use (PAYU) offerings, and increasing adoption of the Data-as-a-Service (DaaS) and freemium models. A dynamic pricing advisory mechanism, supported by user interaction metrics and data usage analytics, will further enhance the platform's ability to align pricing with customer value and market conditions.

Finally, scaling the business model requires continuous pilot validation and feedback integration. By leveraging insights from pilot projects and early adopters, the marketplace can adapt its offerings and governance framework to address emerging trends and user expectations, partly as co-creation, or semi co-creation (e.g. hackathons, community funding programs, etc.). This iterative approach ensures that the FAME Marketplace remains responsive and competitive, maintaining its position as a leading platform for secure and efficient data exchange.

4.3 Market Competition

The FAME Marketplace operates in a competitive landscape defined by a diverse range of data marketplaces, each employing unique business models, features, and technological capabilities. To assess its position, a comprehensive comparison with existing platforms is essential, utilizing insights

from foundational studies ([1], [2], and [3]) that provide extensive surveys and pricing analyses of data marketplaces. These analyses shed light on the evolving trends and strategies in the market, forming a foundation for competitor evaluation.

4.3.1 Marketplace Characteristics

Data marketplaces can be broadly categorized into sell-side, buy-side, and two-sided markets. Sell-side markets facilitate the sale of data from multiple providers to consumers, while buy-side markets allow individuals and organizations to monetize their data by enabling acquisition by data dealers. Two-sided marketplaces, such as FAME, integrate both mechanisms, allowing data providers to list their assets in a catalog and enabling individuals and organizations to purchase data using blockchain-based payment transactions. This dual functionality enhances the platform's versatility and appeals to a broader range of users.

4.3.2 Data Categories and Specialization

FAME differentiates itself by its federated structure, which enables it to cater to three main categories of data: open data repositories, generalized-purpose data, and niche specialized datasets. This capability allows FAME to attract a diverse range of users and data providers, offering a unified platform for various data needs under one umbrella. Competitors often specialize in one or two categories, limiting their scope compared to the comprehensive offerings of FAME.

4.3.3 Centralized vs. Decentralized Models

Most traditional marketplaces, such as Amazon AWS Data Exchange and Snowflake Data Marketplace, employ centralized models. While these models are advantageous in terms of efficiency, privacy, and responsive user interfaces, they often limit transactional autonomy. For example, centralized platforms typically control billing, collections, and payment disbursements, charging referral fees and enforcing rigid pricing models. Moreover, vendor lock-in is a likely consequence of centralized models: services are offered in a very marketplace-specific manner, herewith complicating marketplace switch processes.

In contrast, FAME's blockchain-based architecture offers transactional autonomy, allowing data providers to conduct transactions directly with their customers using tokenized digital currencies. FAME also enables dynamic pricing mechanisms and supports smart contract-based governance using ERC20, ERC721, and ERC1155 token standards. This transparency and flexibility foster fair pricing and improve market efficiency, positioning FAME as a cutting-edge alternative to traditional centralized marketplaces.

4.3.4 Storage and Compute Services

Competitors like Amazon, Snowflake, and Databricks offer integrated compute and storage services alongside their data marketplaces. This coupling allows users to buy, store, and process large datasets within a unified infrastructure, enhancing efficiency and performance for big data applications. Coupling the marketplace to storage and compute services puts the data sovereignty of users at stake however, as especially data storage generates a long-term dependency on the hosting provider, and through this, intrudes into one of the core values of a data space, being data sovereignty. While FAME does not provide such services, its focus on federated data exchange and blockchain-based transactions allows it to concentrate on providing unmatched flexibility, security, and innovation in data monetization. Focusing on the data exchange, the data sovereignty core value is not questioned, and there is no penalty for using the marketplace in persisting data on the premise of the data provider.

4.3.5 Digital Asset Pricing Support

It aims to extract both subjective and objective information impacting the final price. Additionally, it provides the functionality to offer price ranges based on similar assets for which prices have

historically been determined. Thus, the end-user can view the potential price range within which the price of an asset or digital product may fluctuate. FAME’s PAT uses the questionnaire with specific questions to calculate intrinsic value of the digital asset (this is Value-based pricing mechanism) for two broad groups: datasets and digital products. The value of the digital asset is based on the several dimensions - Estimated cost for the customer, quality (measured: by accuracy, validity, and completeness of the digital asset), costs of creation, volume of customers, uniqueness/rarity, and environmental sustainability (CO2). FAME's unique approach for formulation of suggestion to pricing strategy for digital assets is considering Cost-Plus Pricing strategy enriching the profit margin element considering value-based approach. The Pricing Advisory Tool also provides information on the price of similar assets.

Digital Asset Pricing Approach in FAME

The **Pricing Approach in FAME** presents a structured methodology for determining digital asset pricing by integrating theoretical foundations, cost considerations, and demand-based adjustments. The first step involves a **theoretical approach**, likely incorporating economic pricing models and industry benchmarks to establish an initial pricing framework. The second step, **considering business costs**, ensures that pricing remains sustainable by incorporating **Questionnaire-Based Cost Estimation (QBS)**, which gathers cost-related insights directly from relevant stakeholders. This method allows for more precise cost assessments, improving the accuracy of the pricing strategy. The third step enhances pricing adaptability through **Similarity Analysis Tools**, which compare digital assets with similar offerings to refine price estimates. The fourth steps considers the dynamicity with respect to the evolving data assets and their usage on FAME. In this step, the concept of network-based eigenvector centrality is used to account for the dynamic changes in the price estimates. Finally, the geometric average of prices computed in steps three and four is taken to suggest a price for the focal data asset. This mechanism helps adjust prices dynamically based on market demand and competitor pricing trends, ensuring that the valuation remains competitive and responsive. By combining theoretical models, direct cost analysis, and data-driven demand adjustments, the FAME pricing approach provides a comprehensive and flexible method for setting digital asset prices. This structured approach helps businesses optimize revenue while maintaining fairness and transparency in the data marketplace.

4.3.6 Embedded Financial Solutions

Another distinctive feature of FAME is its role as an embedded finance solution. By bridging tokenized digital currencies and traditional fiat money gateways, FAME enables seamless payment for data assets via wallets such as MetaMask. This functionality ensures accessibility for both blockchain-savvy users and those relying on traditional financial systems, enhancing its usability and market reach.

4.3.7 Competitive Edge

FAME's unique value propositions, including its decentralized model, support for diverse data categories, and innovative financial mechanisms, set it apart from competitors such as Amazon AWS Data Exchange, Snowflake Data Marketplace, and Datum. While these platforms excel in offering compute and storage integration, FAME prioritizes user autonomy, fair pricing, and blockchain-powered transparency. These strengths enable FAME to carve a niche in the data marketplace ecosystem, attracting users and providers seeking a flexible, secure, and dynamic platform for data exchange.

By continuously refining its offerings and addressing emerging user needs, FAME is well-positioned to remain competitive in a rapidly evolving market, leveraging its innovative features to deliver sustained value to its users and stakeholders.

5 Challenges and Risks

Every business model may bear certain risks that the fundamental blueprint of how the service aims to deliver its value has material weaknesses and does not lead to sustainable operation. It is crucial to identify these risks and implement mitigation measures to manage the risks properly.

The FAME Marketplace incorporates multiple innovative elements, so to a certain degree the underlying business model is comparable with a start-up introducing new ways of operating to the market.

5.1 Risks

In addition to risks related to more general business models, there are risks arising specifically from providing innovation for a new market which are discussed in detail in the following sections.

5.1.1 Market Risks

Unproven Demand: The target market of the FAME Marketplace may not fully understand or see the value in the innovation, leading to low adoption rates.

Market Misalignment: The product or service may not meet the specific needs or preferences of the new market. The data-driven business models of the marketplace's customer is also pretty new and need to be understood to serve them right.

Cultural Barriers: Differences in cultural norms, behaviors, or regulations may hinder acceptance of innovation. Cultural norms are also relevant from a business perspective where certain mindsets and success patterns are established in the different industries which may slow down the process of establishing trust in the platform.

Slow Adoption: New markets may be resistant to change, leading to slower-than-expected adoption of the innovation. Which plays directly into the revenue model and financial plan of the marketplace operation.

5.1.2 Financial Risks

High Initial Costs: Developing and introducing innovation often requires significant upfront investment in R&D, marketing, and distribution. This addresses the ratio of initial costs to the expected revenue within the timeline to establish the marketplace until break even.

Cash Flow Challenges: Long sales cycles or delayed revenue streams can strain the startup's finances. The overall budget of the ramp-up phase until the revenue is able to carry the marketplace with sufficient reserves for the volatility of the cashflow.

Uncertain ROI: The return on investment may be uncertain, especially if the market takes longer to mature than anticipated. Which is close to the first point in this section but now the ratio of investment to any payback event (dividends, sale, M&A, etc.)

Funding Gaps: Difficulty in securing additional funding if early results are not promising. There is a planning mistake regarding buffering the risks and anticipated challenges of the market approach with a solid funding plan but also cost vs. delivery plan of the marketplace.

5.1.3 Operational Risks

Scaling Challenges: If the marketplace grows more rapidly in new markets than expected that may strain the marketplace's operational capacity and resources. The delivery cannot follow in quantity and quality the customers demand and makes a growing customer churning and unreachable.

Supply Chain Issues: Dependence on third-party suppliers or partners in unfamiliar markets can lead to delays or disruptions. That is specifically relevant for the platform because it incorporates multiple technologies where the vendors themselves are in a phase of establishing new services.

Talent Shortages: Difficulty in finding skilled talent who understand both the innovation and the new market. This needs to be seen against the background of a growing market of the underlying technologies (decentralized identity, blockchain technology, tokenized assets, zero-knowledge technology, data-driven services, etc.) where tough competition for talents in a relatively small pool of resources is to be expected.

5.1.4 Competitive Risks

Emerging Competitors: Other companies may quickly replicate or improve upon the innovation, eroding the startup's competitive edge. As the current situation implies the marketplace is still early in the window of opportunity and can potentially set standards which brings the advantage of the first mover. Nevertheless, the risk is an inherent part of market developments.

Established Players: Incumbent companies in the new market may leverage their resources and customer base to outcompete the FAME Marketplace. It is currently not foreseeable how big tech players like Amazon, Microsoft, Google, and others act if they recognize the business as relevant for their own revenue model.

Price Wars: Competitors may undercut pricing, making it difficult for the startup to sustain profitability.

5.1.5 Regulatory and Legal Risks

Compliance Challenges: Navigating unfamiliar regulatory environments can be complex and costly. This is even more true if certain regulatory frameworks are not put into force yet (FiDA, EUDI implementation act) or in the process of review (PSR, PSD3).

Intellectual Property (IP) Risks: The innovation may not be adequately protected, leading to IP theft or infringement. Many building blocks of the platform materialized a huge amount of intellectual work and investments. That value may be understood and copied by third parties.

Policy Changes: Sudden changes in local laws or regulations could disrupt operations or increase costs.

5.1.6 Technological Risks

Technology Obsolescence: Rapid advancements in technology may render the innovation outdated before it gains traction. This is specifically relevant for technologies like blockchain, NFT technology, zero-knowledge tech stacks, authentication procedures, and identity schemes, as these areas undergo currently a massive development. The market in these areas moves very quickly and it needs to be understood which technologies converge and become mature and which are not moving in that direction.

Implementation Challenges: The innovation may face technical issues or require significant customization for the new market. This is true as some technologies need to be tested and to provide proof in the fields.

Cybersecurity Threats: Vulnerabilities in technology could expose the FAME Marketplace to data breaches or other cyber risks.

5.1.7 Reputational Risks

Brand Misunderstanding: The marketplace's brand or innovation may be misunderstood or misrepresented in the new market. In addition, some data providers may not act in a good faith or put the reputation of the marketplace at risk by their activities.

Negative Feedback: There is also the spread of the word between customers, where early failures or poor customer experiences can damage the marketplace's reputation and hinder future growth.

Ethical Concerns: Specifically, regarding the important role of AI or data analysis services, ethical standards are still moving and developed over time in the European society. The innovation may raise ethical or social concerns in the new market, leading to backlash.

5.1.8 Strategic Risks

Misaligned Partnerships: Collaborating with the wrong partners in the new market can lead to conflicts or inefficiencies.

Overexpansion: Expanding too quickly into multiple markets can dilute focus and resources.

Pivoting Challenges: The marketplace may need to pivot its strategy on the way to a profitable and scalable business but doing so in a new market can be risky and costly.

5.1.9 Customer Risks

Lack of Trust: Customers in new markets may be hesitant to trust an unfamiliar marketplace service or innovation.

Education Costs: Significant resources may be required to educate the market about the marketplace's benefits. The marketplace is a service that requires explanation, training and a good documentation. Also, the role of an underlying infrastructure for the customer acquisition and product provision may be a big task for potential customers.

Customer Support Challenges: Providing adequate customer support in a new market can be logistically difficult.

5.1.10 Macroeconomic Risks

Economic Instability: Economic downturns or currency fluctuations in the new market can impact demand and profitability.

Political Instability: Changes in government, trade policies, or geopolitical tensions can disrupt operations.

Pandemic or Natural Disasters: Unforeseen global or local events can severely impact market conditions.

5.2 Mitigation Strategies

To reduce these risks, the FAME Marketplace can in general perform the following activities:

- Create Proof of Concepts (PoCs) and pilot with potential customers and prospects to create showcases others can understand and apply to their business more easily.
- Build strong local partnerships and networks to accelerate the reach-out to the market and time-to-market.
- Secure intellectual property protections and simultaneously apply an opensource strategy to support and accelerate the integration as well as adoption.
- Develop a flexible business model that can adapt to market feedback. This includes the pricing strategy and the configuration of the pricing module.
- Maintain a strong financial buffer to weather uncertainties.
- Invest in customer education and trust-building initiatives.

The following sections provide more specifically mitigation measures with respect to the risks listed in the section above.

5.2.1 Market Risks Mitigation

Unproven Demand: FAME leverages pilots and early pilot customers to fully understand the need, requirements, and churns. Also, we test the value proposition on many occasions like industry events, webinars, and joint working groups with other sister projects.

Market Misalignment: In addition to the pilots FAME is also investing into the analysis of the market adoption of the used services, e.g. tokenization technologies, EUDI wallet infrastructure, the AI-driven market, etc.; specifically on how customers adopt these new technologies.

Cultural Barriers: The international and cross-industry team of FAME provides inherently for the inclusion of cultural norms on multiple levels. In the user tests and hackathons, the mindsets and industry-specific know-how are tested.

Slow Adoption: This is indeed a high risk as the marketplace connects to the core business of its customers, and despite the help the marketplace can provide it needs to be understood and a certain adoption baseline. To accelerate this phase, FAME tries to acquire customers in the earliest possible state and win them for a co-creation of the final phase and safe time.

5.2.2 Financial Risks Mitigation

High Initial Costs: FAME tries to cut these initial costs by identifying the MVP scope to avoid to invest into unnecessary features, and leverage the power of its consortia members as well as the strong bonds to other consortia in the EU HORIZEN ecosystem to save the most relevant costs in the case of the marketplace: customer acquisition.

Uncertain ROI: The measures applied to High Initial Costs include the mitigation of the Uncertain ROI risk to a certain degree. There is no exit strategy comparable to a startup venture, nevertheless the participation on the revenue of the marketplace and possible privileged usage of the marketplace IP pays into the return of the investment made to establish the FAME Marketplace.

Funding Gaps: There is a very clear budget plan and cost tracking to avoid gaps between the funding capital and the actual costs. The remaining risks are managed by the participants of the FAME consortium.

5.2.3 Operational Risks

Scaling Challenges: The founding members in the FAME consortium are well established and experienced market participants. They have capabilities to support the scaling phase of the marketplace in the case the marketplace grows faster than anticipated.

Supply Chain Issues: Nevertheless, there are dependencies on third-party suppliers or partners which can lead to delays and disruptions as the FAME Marketplace establishes many partnerships. A multi-vendor strategy will be relevant once the platform scales and the operational risk management adopts to this growth.

Talent Shortages: Given the current situation and referring to Draghi's report on Europe's competitiveness the problem of talent shortage is a real threat to high tech and innovation businesses, which will be mitigated by 2 measures: 1) FAME's consortium members are well established and can leverage their pan-European recruiting power and 2) the marketplace incorporates many innovations in a sector that appears highly relevant for carrier planning and may attract young talents to base their carrier in technology services.

5.2.4 Competitive Risks

Emerging Competitors: There will be many different forms of distributing channels in data driven business models, where FAME will use the windows of opportunity to set standards and occupy the market segment as one of the first. Furthermore, FAME's competitive advantage is based on the following which is hard to replicate in short timeframes:

1. Sound regulatory compliance to provide legal certainty to customers
2. Longterm experience in a complex environment to navigate the challenges better than newcomers
3. Focus on proven needs (multiple pilots, sufficient ramp-up timeline, etc.) and cost efficiency for high margins

Established Players: Established European players are very slow in adopting and the lack of speed of established players providing innovations in a highly dynamic environment gives FAME a structural advantage, given the speed of adoption is maintained as an inherent part of the marketplace's KPIs. Big global tech companies on the other hand usually hesitate to adopt the regulatory environment in Europe and the specific needs of the European economic perspective (margins, pricing, efficiency, automation, human resources, etc.) They very often fill gaps the traditional industry leaves open by not acting customer oriented. There is a high chance that FAME is able to occupy the market segment and leaving little gaps to be taken over by established big players.

5.2.5 Regulatory and Legal Risks

Compliance Challenges: Already during the design and development phase of the marketplace regulatory developments are carefully considered as compliance to regulatory standards is one of the USPs of the marketplace, e.g. adopting FiDA, eIDAS and its implementation acts, as well as drafts like PSR, PSD3.

Intellectual Property (IP) Risks: IP considerations are actively managed, already as part of the collaboration in the FAME consortium. It is also an established process in most of the consortium members and this capability is protecting the platform to a certain degree against legal surprises related to IP claims and helping the platform to defend itself in the case should an IP claim being raised.

Policy Changes: Some consortium members are very well connected to regulatory policy making bodies and procedures implying that the FAME Marketplace should be well informed ahead of implementation time.

5.2.6 Technological Risks

Technology Obsolescence: The technology the platform is currently build on is very innovative and some parts even in an early stage and at the beginning of their market maturity life cycle, e.g. EU Identity protocols, crypto algorithms for blockchain components, NFT stacks, etc. Nevertheless, the FAME team observes the developments and monitor of some early technologies may be replaced by others, more suitable ones; and consider to follow the new developments if required.

Implementation Challenges: The FAME team is very experienced regarding integration projects and the inherent aim is to make the adoption as easy as possible for platform customers. Based on this experience the new technology are wrapped into processes to simplify tests and sandboxing for customers to save time and resources during ramp-up phase.

Cybersecurity Threats: The monitoring and responding to the new cybersecurity threats is a very important part of the platform's resilience procedures. The regulatory environment of the marketplace's customers, e.g. financial services, cloud services, digital health services, include strict rules on the cybersecurity resilience (DORA, PSD2/PSR, NIS-2, etc.) which helps to mitigate the cybersecurity risk by the inherent environment setup.

5.2.7 Reputational Risks

Brand Misunderstanding: The marketplace's brand or innovation may be misunderstood or misrepresented in the new market. In addition, some data providers may not act in a good faith or put the reputation of the marketplace at risk by their activities.

Negative Feedback: There is also the spread of the word between customers, where early failures or poor customer experiences can damage the marketplace's reputation and hinder future growth.

Ethical Concerns: Specifically, regarding the important role of AI or data analysis services, ethical standards are still moving and developed over time in the European society. The innovation may raise ethical or social concerns in the new market, leading to backlash.

5.2.8 Strategic Risks

Misaligned Partnerships: Collaborating with the wrong partners in the new market can lead to conflicts or inefficiencies.

Overexpansion: Expanding too quickly into multiple markets can dilute focus and resources.

Pivoting Challenges: The marketplace may need to pivot its strategy on the way to a profitable and scalable business, but doing so in a new market can be risky and costly.

5.2.9 Customer Risks

Lack of Trust: FAME is putting significant efforts into training of stakeholders, learning content, and documentation including articles to mitigate the trust risk.

Education Costs: As education is an important part of the project during all phases from design to market approach this risk is prominently handled and gets adequate resources. The efforts regarding customer acquisition are shared between consortium members during the development phase and prioritized part of the operational task after go-live.

Customer Support Challenges: This risk of providing adequate customer support in a new market is currently hard to predict and measures need to be adjusted once the project goes operational.

5.2.10 Macroeconomic Risks

Economic Instability: As the market for the FAME Marketplace is pan-European there are certain geographical buffers within the European markets to mitigate economic instabilities to a certain degree. Nevertheless, potential customers are not limited to be based in Europe and once established the marketplace can also serve global customers.

Political Instability: In the current global environment with increased tension between the world's biggest economies this risk is harder to manage and requires careful attention, specifically on new policies on digital services, international trading, and operational resilience.

Pandemic or Natural Disasters: There are natural disasters which impact more than just a region, e.g. the volcano eruptions in Iceland impacting the international air traffic, or COVID-19 impacting the human resource situation in nearly all organizations worldwide. The FAME Marketplace is utilizing distributed technologies, for example multi-region cloud infrastructures, distributed ledgers, SSI-credentials, and NFT technologies, which are technologies that are much more resilient to pandemic or natural disasters than traditional web2 technologies.

By proactively addressing these risks, the marketplace can increase its chances of successfully introducing innovation to new markets.

6 Legal and Security Landscape

6.1 Regulatory Framework

As FAME intends to promote the monetization and access of data in relation to financial activities, it would need to closely observe any legal provisions regulating the financial sector, and those concerning the governance of data in general. In addition, other legislation may also be applicable because of the access to certain services and products FAME intends to provide to Marketplace participants (e.g., AI or authentication of people and organizations). Most of the legislation mentioned below is currently binding, while some are yet to enter into force. The overview provided below builds on Deliverable 1.3 ‘Ethical Management and Regulatory Compliance’ Framework I submitted on M18 and provides an update regarding the relevant enforcement dates for each piece of legislation.

6.1.1 The Framework for Financial Data Access (FiDA)

FiDA proposes a system that provides open access, sharing and use to various categories of business’, and individuals’ customer data, as expressed in Art. 1 and listed in Art. 2. Its primary focus is on consumer interests, promoting competition, security, and trust. It builds on the already existing ‘open banking’ access to customer data held by account-servicing PSPs and takes a customer-centric approach, with effective tools ensuring personal data protection in line with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) for consumers and firms to control their financial data and applying general business-to-business data sharing principles in line with the Data Act. If the services provided by FAME are considered ‘financial information services’, and FAME is considered a FIS provider (as described under Art. 3), FiDA will be directly applicable to the FAME Marketplace. In addition, a considerable number of potential participants may be subject to FiDA. Regardless of whether FiDA is directly applicable, FAME intends to include certain functionalities that help participants comply with FiDA, making it a relevant provision. The FiDA proposal has been approved, and negotiations are currently underway between the European Council and Parliament, with legislation adoption expected Mid-2025.

6.1.2 The Payment Service Directive (PSD3) and the Payment Service Regulation (PSR)

PSD3 is a revision of PSD2 that focuses primarily on payment account data, aimed at regulating newer payment providers and services (internet, mobile, card) to further open the financial market, while ensuring a high protection level for payment service users across all Member States. Payment Service Directive and Payment Service Regulation (PSD3/PSR) contain harmonizing rules on licensing and supervision related to a wider range of providers of payment services, including non-banking Payment Institutions (PIs) and Payment Service Providers (PSPs). This provision is relevant, assuming FAME only allows licensed, supervised payment service providers on its platform to which consumers will have direct access. The PSD3/PSR enforcement is expected towards the end of 2026.

6.1.3 Digital Operational Resilience Act

The Digital Operational Resilience Act seeks to promote the protection of the financial sector, which has become increasingly dependent on technology and tech companies to deliver their services, making it vulnerable to cyber-attacks and incidents. DORA harmonizes digital operational resilience rules, covering ICT risk and third-party risk management, framework, monitoring, digital operational resilience testing, ICT related incidents reporting, information and intelligence sharing on cyber threats, and an oversight framework for critical ICT Third Party Providers (CTPPs). Although DORA is not likely to apply to FAME, its principles may be of relevance from the design phase of its architecture and components, through to the development, testing and continuous improvement of the FAME, and may also provide guidance for the development of the compliance tools. The Digital Operational Resilience Act will apply as of January 17, 2025.

6.1.4 General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

GDPR lays down the rules for the protection of individuals' personal data regarding the processing of personal data and rules relating to the free movement of personal data. It applies to the processing of personal data, wholly or partly by automated means, and processing of personal data that is not automated and forms part of a filing system/ intended to form part of a filing system, by a person or an entity within the EU. This includes processing activities outside the EU that relate to personal data of individuals in the EU. As the data processing services offered on FAME are intended to process more than one hundred data assets in a federated marketplace, the GDPR would be of relevance, as these data-sets are likely to include personal data.

6.1.5 Data Governance Act (DGA)

The DGA plays a central role in the EU's plan to make Europe fit for the digital age and to facilitate Europe's digital transformation by 2030. It aims to improve the conditions for the sharing of data between organisations within the EU to support the use of data research and innovation purposes. Since public entities and organisations generate large amounts of data on a daily basis, the DGA seeks to make use of the combined value of such data to facilitate innovation and economic growth. FAME aims to create a data marketplace for secure sharing and trading of data assets, facilitating the valuation and monetization of financial data. Given the nature of the services, it intends to provide, FAME is likely to fall within the scope of the definition of a 'data intermediation service' (as described under article 2 (11)). The regulation has legal effect as of 24 September 2023.

6.1.6 Data Act

The Data Act complements the DGA by clarifying access and user rights that are attached to certain categories of data with the objective of ensuring fairness in the European data economy. It sets essential requirements for the free movement of (non-personal) data, data sharing mechanisms and services, and for Common European data spaces. It also seeks to enable access to high-quality data and facilitate business-to-business (B2B) and business-to-consumer (B2C) data sharing. The requirements regarding data interoperability, data sharing mechanisms and services, for common European data spaces and smart contracts (for executing data sharing agreements) would be applicable to FAME. In particular, the FAME data exchange and trading offerings are likely to be subject to the interoperability requirements in the Data Act. The Data Act entered into force on 11 January 2024, and it will have legal effect from 12 September 2025.

6.1.7 The EIDAS2 Regulation

The Digital Identity Regulation (EIDAS2) regulation intends to promote universal access for people and businesses to secure and trustworthy electronic identification means and authentication. It aims to instill an adequate level of security in the context of electronic identification and trust services. Eidas2 facilitates secure cross-border transactions by establishing a framework for trust services, website authentication solutions and for digital identity and authentication (Digital Identity Wallet), while instilling confidence in electronic interactions and promoting seamless digital services in the EU. E-IDAS2 also empowers citizens by putting them in control of the use and sharing of their data, supporting and contributing to social empowerment, citizen participation, and inclusivity, which happen to be some of the key principles of FAME. e-IDAS2 is relevant to FAME as it enables and enhances easy and secure cross-border e-ID usage, which will further strengthen the activities on offer on the FAME Marketplace (through Citizen Wallets, and FAME's EmFi products and services), while enhancing consumer empowerment and participation, fostering diversity and inclusivity. eIDAS entered into force in May 2024.

FAME's data focus, coupled with its use of different novel technologies (e.g., AI, blockchain and semantic interoperability), mean it needs to fulfill a range of legal obligations, both in the field of

finance and data. Particular attention needs to be paid to the Data Governance Act and Data Act, which govern data sharing in a broader sense, as well as to the GDPR (concerning personal data) which are likely to apply to FAME. The DSA regulates intermediary services such as hosting platforms, which could have a specific impact on the FAME Marketplace. The introduction of PSD3/PSR opens access to payment data, and promotes customer protection, which may be applicable if licensed, supervised payment service providers (to which consumers will have direct access via the platform) are permitted on the FAME Marketplace. The AI Act sets out certain requirements for developers and deployers of high-risk AI systems but is not directly relevant.

6.2 Security Risks

Ensuring data security is a critical mission of FAME, for which dedicated regulatory provisions come into play. Risks include potential data breaches or unauthorized access. Robust encryption, secure payment systems, and regular security audits will help mitigate these risks.

There are specific provisions that provide certain obligations for legal entities to safeguard against ICT-related incidents. As expressed above the Digital Operations Resilience Act seeks to promote the protection of financial entities from vulnerabilities created by an increased reliance on technology and tech companies. DORA includes strict rules to safeguard financial institutions from ICT-incidents. However, despite its promotion of the exchange of financial data, DORA may not extend to FAME as the latter would not necessarily be considered to be a 'financial entity'. The obligations in DORA would however extend to the participants of FAME (who are financial entities). Instead, the second Network and Information Security (NIS2) directive, which governs cybersecurity provides some provisions that may be more applicable to FAME with regard to its risk management integration. Art. 21 NIS2 is a fundamental cybersecurity provision and is especially relevant in the context of FAME.

Article 21 discusses requirements for cybersecurity risk-management measures, highlighting the importance of taking appropriate technical, operational and organisational measures to manage risk under article 21(1). Article 21(2) set out measures that need to be integrated into risk management plans:

- Need to develop policies on risk analysis and information system security
- Develop procedures for handling incidents
- Business continuity, such as backup management and disaster recovery, and crisis management
- Supply chain security, including security-related aspects concerning the relationship between each entity and its direct suppliers or service providers
- Security in network and information systems acquisition, development and maintenance, including vulnerability handling and disclosure
- Policies and procedures to assess the effectiveness of cybersecurity risk-management measures
- Basic cyber hygiene practices and cybersecurity training
- Policies and procedures regarding the use of cryptographic and, where appropriate, encryption
- Human resources security, access control policies and asset management
- The use of multi-factor authentication or continuous authentication solutions, secured voice, video and text communications and secured emergency communication systems within the entity, where appropriate

7 Case Studies and Examples

7.1 Successful Business Models

The development of the FAME Marketplace has drawn inspiration from several successful business models in the data marketplace ecosystem. Two illustrative examples highlight the potential of diverse approaches to monetizing data exchange platforms:

Example 1: A Data Marketplace for AI Model Training Datasets

This platform specializes in providing high-quality, curated datasets for training machine learning models. Businesses across various industries purchase these datasets to enhance the accuracy and performance of their AI applications. The marketplace leverages its expertise in data curation and quality assurance to build trust and meet the stringent requirements of its target audience. By focusing on a niche demand—AI training data—it has become indispensable for companies pursuing AI-driven innovation.

Example 2: A Subscription-Based Platform Offering Real-Time Market Data and Analytics

Another successful model involves a subscription-based service that provides real-time financial market data and analytics. This platform caters to businesses seeking actionable insights for strategic decision-making. Through tiered subscription plans, it ensures accessibility to a broad customer base, from small enterprises to large corporations. The integration of cutting-edge analytics tools and a user-friendly interface further boosts customer retention, demonstrating the effectiveness of combining premium data with robust usability.

Example 3: Blockchain-Based Decentralized Marketplace

A third example is a blockchain-powered decentralized data marketplace that facilitates direct transactions between data providers and consumers. The platform emphasizes transactional autonomy, allowing users to set their own prices and terms. It supports multiple token standards for payments and employs smart contracts for governance, ensuring transparency and efficiency. This model appeals to privacy-conscious users and industries requiring secure, auditable transactions, such as healthcare and finance. Revenue is generated through transaction fees and optional premium services, such as enhanced analytics or private data-sharing agreements.

Example 4: Niche Data Exchange for Specialized Industries

This marketplace focuses on providing specialized data for industries such as agriculture, healthcare, or energy. By catering to niche audiences, it offers highly relevant datasets, such as crop yield forecasts for farmers or renewable energy usage trends for policymakers. The marketplace differentiates itself through domain expertise, customer support, and the ability to aggregate and analyze data to generate actionable insights. Revenue is driven by licensing agreements, pay-as-you-use models, and strategic partnerships with industry leaders.

Example 5: Data Marketplace for Online Advertisement Data

In a data marketplace for web advertising, individual consumers and organizations can sell their data at fair, model-agnostic prices determined by its predictive value. An online retailer looking to optimize its recommendation algorithm can purchase aggregated consumer transaction data from a Data Management Platform. Using algorithmic mechanisms, the value of data is dynamically assessed based on its contribution to the retailer's predictive model. If a dataset substantially improves purchase predictions, it is priced higher, ensuring sellers are compensated fairly. For instance, financial institutions might subscribe to real-time consumer credit behavior data, where pricing adjusts based on its utility in fraud detection models.

7.2 Lessons Learned

The analysis of these successful data marketplaces reveals key lessons that are critical for shaping the FAME Marketplace:

Trust and Transparency:

Building trust through transparent operations and clear communication is vital. Data providers and consumers must feel confident in the integrity, security, and value of the transactions occurring on the platform.

Security and Compliance:

Prioritizing data security and aligning with regulatory standards are fundamental to long-term success. Regular compliance checks and adaptability to evolving regulations are non-negotiable in maintaining the platform's reputation and operational continuity.

Unique and High-Demand Data:

Offering exclusive, high-demand datasets attract customers and differentiates a marketplace from competitors. The focus should be on curating data that is difficult to obtain elsewhere or that provides significant value to its users.

Scalability and Adaptability:

A successful marketplace must scale effectively to meet increasing user demand and diversify its offerings. Flexibility in business models, such as incorporating subscription plans, pay-as-you-go options, or freemium services, can help accommodate varying customer needs.

Continuous Innovation:

Finally, successful data marketplaces emphasize the importance of ongoing innovation. By integrating emerging technologies, such as AI-driven insights or blockchain for transactional autonomy, platforms can remain competitive and address evolving user expectations.

This approach will position FAME for long-term success in the competitive data marketplace landscape.

8 Linked Documents

- 1- Legal and Security Framework Documentation - <https://zenodo.org/records/15591094>
- 2- FAME Whitepaper 'FAME: A Federated Secured, Trusted and Interoperable Marketplace and Data Space' - <https://zenodo.org/records/14216810>
- 3- Whitepaper 'Monetizing Data in International Data Spaces: Business Concepts and Technical Enablers' - <https://zenodo.org/records/14845137>
- 4- D4.2-Pricing, Trading and Monetization Techniques - <https://zenodo.org/records/15311413>
- 5- D4.3-Operational Models, Business Models and Governance I - <https://zenodo.org/records/15310303>